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Subjective and Objective VQA of Video Codecs for UHD Video Streaming

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Abstract—In this work, we conduct a subjective video quality assessment (VQA) experiment to evaluate the performance of modern video codecs when displayed on a large (30sqm) ultra-high-definition (UHD) video wall. Our comparative study involves four encoding standards: Advanced Video Coding (AVC) / H.264, High-Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) / H.265, Versatile Video Coding (VVC) / H.266, and AOMedia Video 1 (AV1). Moreover, the study includes the evaluation in terms of correlation performance of a set of widely used full-reference objective VQA metrics against the subjective scores. Our results showcase the perceptual superiority of the VVC over rival encoding standards, aligning with the objective quality assessment and relevant literature.

Keywords—Video Quality Assessment (VQA), Video Compression, Subjective Study, UHD (4K)

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid evolution of digital media applications has seen associated increases in video content resolutions and display technologies to provide sceneries with exceptional sharpness and clarity. The latter transformed the visual experience of users by offering 4K (3840 x 2160 pixels) Ultra-High-Definition (UHD) resolution and beyond. However, this brings about new challenges for storing and transmitting videos. The high data rates concerning 4K video streaming have amplified the role of video compression, making it essential to reduce both the network and the storage requirements to reasonable levels. Widespread video codecs such as Advanced Video

Coding (AVC) / H.264 [1] and High-Efficiency Video Coding (HEVC) / H.265 [2] have been utilized over the past decades to efficiently compress Standard-Definition (SD) and High-Definition (HD) videos. However, the proliferation of UHD videos, linked with the prevalence of video communication applications that now dominate internet traffic, have triggered the need for new video compression standards. The AV1 [3] and the Versatile Video Coding (VVC) / H.266 [4] video codecs have been developed in recent years to enhance compression capabilities and to accommodate a diverse set of video applications, including 360° video coding [5].

Video compression inherently degrades the quality of video sequences and affects the users' experience. Therefore, video quality assessment (VQA) methods aim to estimate the quality of video content as perceived by the end users [6]. Objective full-reference (FR) VQA methods estimate the perceptual quality by comparing the impaired video sequence to the reference (unimpaired) one based on pixel values and/or statistical spatio-temporal features derived from the video frames. Subjective VQA methods, on the other hand, provide more reliable results where the scores are obtained through experiments with human participants. In [7], a subjective quality assessment experiment was carried out to evaluate the performance of HEVC for 4K-UHD TV broadcasting services. Another study by [8] compared the performance of different video encoders on 4K video content and assessed the accuracy of objective VQA models against subjective scores.

Fig. 1 Video image examples, Video Resolution: 3840x2160, Frame Rate: 30 fps, Format: yuv420p [9].

Fig. 2 Temporal Information (TI) (y-axis) and Spatial Information (SI) (x-axis), show the complexity of the selected reference video sequences.

Different from previous studies, we carried out a subjective VQA experiment to assess the quality of 4K videos projected on a large video wall. Our experiment involved testing four different video codecs, including AV1 and VVC codecs, across various quality levels. In section II of this article, we present the video sequences used in our experiment and provide details of the encoding process. The experimental setup of our subjective VQA study is presented along with a discussion of the key findings in Section III. Section IV investigates the correlation between different objective VQA metrics and the MOS for popular correlation indices. Finally, we summarize and conclude our work in Section V.

II. VIDEO DATASET & ENCODING SETTINGS

A. Selection of Reference Videos

The video dataset used in the present study consists of ten videos [9]. However, due to the lengthy duration of the experiment, which could extend beyond three hours and therefore be exhausting for the participants, a smaller set of five sequences was selected. Video image captions of the examined video scenes appear in Fig. 1. The videos are in YUV format and have a 4K resolution (3840x2160) at 30 frames per second and a duration of 10 seconds each.

To ensure that the five sequences are diverse in their content and spatio-temporal features, we performed an analysis of the videos' spatial and temporal activity. To quantify the scene characteristics, the Spatial Information (SI) and Temporal Information (TI) metrics were obtained [10][11]. These metrics are crucial for analyzing the complexity of video sequences. The obtained SI and TI metrics are illustrated in Fig. 2. The figure suggests that the video sequences exhibit diverse spatio-temporal complexities and span a wide range of the SI-TI space. The SI and TI metrics were an important factor in selecting the reference sequences in our experiment. Our selected set consists of the Bund Nightscape, Rush Hour, Fountains, Marathon, and Tall Buildings videos. Notice that the videos Rush Hour and Tall Buildings have the largest difference in both spatial and temporal features.

B. Test Sequences - Encoding Configurations

Each video was encoded with AVC, HEVC (using the libx264 and libx265 builds from ffmpeg (v.6.1.1), respectively), VVC (Fraunhofer's VVenc v.1.8.0) and SVT-

Fig. 3 Image capture during the VQA Experiment

AV1 (v.1.8.0) encoders, using constant quality encoding and five quantization parameters (QP). The encodings were performed using a 64-bit Windows 10 (v.22 H2) machine, consisting of a 12th Gen Intel(R) Core (TM) i9-12900K (16 cores, 3.20 GHz). Since the QP ranges are not unified for all codecs (e.g., HEVC: 0-51, SVT-AV1: 1-63), the experimental configuration was established following the relevant literature to allow for a fair and objective comparison of the investigated video codecs [12][13][14][15]. As a result, the SVT-AV1 codec involved QPs of 27, 35, 46, 55, and 62 while the x264, x265, and VVC codecs employed matching QPs of 22, 27, 32, 37, and 42. The aim was to adapt to and investigate a wide range of typical bandwidths, as indicated by the literature. The medium preset parameter was used for x264, x265, and VVC while -preset 5 was used for SVT-AV1. The same intra-update of 48 frames was utilized for all the codecs.

III. SUBJECTIVE VQA EXPERIMENT

A. Subjective VQA Setup

A total of 27 participants took part in the assessment, 16 males and 11 females, between 20 and 65 years old, with an average age of 30. During the subjective VQA test we adopted the specifications given by ITU-T, Rec. P.910 [10]. The participants were asked to rate 100 video sequences (5 videos x 5 QPs x 4 codecs). The experiment took place in a Virtual Production studio with LED video wall (30sqm) supporting 2160p/ UHD resolution (3840x2160 pixels), for realistic ultra-high definition VQA (see Fig 3). Prior to the actual experiment, we trained the participants in a practice trial where they were required to rate the perceptual quality of video sequences that were not included in our dataset.

During the experiment, the video sequences were displayed in a random order. The degradation category rating (DCR) method or double stimulus impairment scale (DSIS) method [16] which presents stimuli in pairs, was utilized. Therefore, the original / reference video was displayed before each instant of the impaired video. The method specified that after each impaired video, participants had to rate the quality of the video, by filling out a questionnaire. Participants rated the video quality on a 5-point scale, with values ranging from 1 to 5, where lower values correspond to bad quality, and higher values correspond to excellent quality. The experiment was divided into four sessions (one for each codec) and lasted for around one and a half hours. The participants were given a 10-minute break after each session.

TABLE I. SUBJECTIVE BD-RATE SAVINGS (%) BASED ON MOS RATINGS

Subjective BD-RATE %			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-36.248	-46.779	-72.796
SVT-AV1	-	-6.709	-45.549
X265	-	-	-47.291

* Negative values indicate bitrate demands savings.

Fig. 4 Subjective VQA rate-distortion curves: MOS vs Bitrate

B. Processing of Subjective Scores

In this study, the Mean Opinion Score (MOS) served as the subjective metric for measuring quality. Specifically, MOS was used to determine the average of the human subjects' scores. Before calculating the MOS scores, an outlier elimination procedure was followed based on [10] Annex A. We carried out a rate-distortion analysis of the resulting MOS scores which are shown in Fig. 4. We also computed the average bitrate savings of each encoder over the others based on Bjontegaard Delta (BD-Rate) [17]. The obtained results are displayed in Table I. Fig. 4 and Table I show that VVC significantly outperforms all other encoders. The SVT-AV1 appears to be the second best-performing encoder among the investigated encoders. However, SVT-AV1 results were comparable to those of x265, reducing bitrate demands by only 6%. The depicted results align with the objective evaluation analysis we present in Section IV and the relevant literature [12][13][14][15].

IV. OBJECTIVE VIDEO QUALITY ASSESSMENT

A. Calculation of Objective VQA Metrics

We used seven objective video quality assessment metrics to calculate the distortion between the source and the encoded videos. The adopted objective VQA metrics are the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) [13], the structural similarity index measure (SSIM) [18], the Visual Information Fidelity (VIF) [19], the 4K version of the Video Multimethod Assessment Fusion (VMAF-4K) (version 0.6.1) [20][21], the Multi-Scale Structural Similarity (MS-SSIM) [22], the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio taking into account Contrast Sensitivity Function (CSF)

TABLE II. OBJECTIVE BD-RATE SAVINGS (%) BASED ON PSNR PSNR-HSV, PSNR-HSV-M, SSIM, MS-SSIM, VIF, VMAF-4K

Objective BD-RATE % based on PSNR			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-28.92	-39.78	-38.86
SVT-AV1	-	-14.11	-42.09
X265	-	-	-31.58
Objective BD-RATE % based on PSNR-HSV			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-27.18	-34.42	-54.02
SVT-AV1	-	-9.03	-37.26
X265	-	-	-30
Objective BD-RATE % based on PSNR-HSV-M			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-30.5	-32.39	-53.99
SVT-AV1	-	-2.32	-34.74
X265	-	-	-32.57
Objective BD-RATE % based on SSIM			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-28.1	-45.44	-63.56
SVT-AV1	-	-22.92	-49.55
X265	-	-	-33.19
Objective BD-RATE % based on MS-SSIM			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-33.629	-40.134	-59.328
SVT-AV1	-	-7.417	-38.441
X265	-	-	-31.693
Objective BD-RATE % based on VIF			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-32.05	-41.276	-59.91
SVT-AV1	-	-9.623	-37.67
X265	-	-	-29.29
Objective BD-RATE % based on VMAF-4K			
	SVT-AV1	X265	X264
VVC	-22.34	-27.37	-49.04
SVT-AV1	-	-3.31	-31.85
X265	-	-	-29.37

* Negative values indicate savings

(PSNR-HVS) [23] and the Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio taking into account Contrast Sensitivity Function (CSF) and between-coefficient contrast masking of DCT basis functions (PSNR-HVS-M) [24]. The PSNR, SSIM, VIF, and VMAF-4K metrics were obtained using the ffmpeg software. The rest metrics were computed using the Video Quality Measurement Tool (VQMT) [25].

Fig. 5 displays the rate-distortion curves between the bitrate demands and the associated video quality metrics for all encoded video sequences. In addition, BD-Rate measures are provided in Table II to illustrate the bitrate reduction of more efficient codecs while delivering the same objective video quality compared to the less efficient ones. All investigated VQA metrics demonstrated consistent behavior in terms of the best performing video codec(s). As expected, VVC achieved the highest bitrate reduction across all the computed metrics. Specifically, for equivalent PSNR values, VVC reduces the bitrate demands by 35%, 44%, and 76% compared to AV1,

x265, and x264, respectively. SVT-AV1 is the second best performing codec, followed by the x265. However, here it is worth noting that while SVT-AV1 reduces the bitrate requirements over x265 by 14.34% and 22.92%, based on PSNR and SSIM calculations, respectively, when it comes to VMAF-4K, both codecs are closely ranked with SVT-AV1 achieving only a marginal 3.3% bitrate reduction compared to x265. The legacy x264 codec is consistently ranked low in all examined cases, however, it is the most efficient codec in terms of encoding speed (not depicted here).

B. Objective VQA Metrics Correlation to MOS

We used five different methods to evaluate the performance of objective VQA metrics in terms of their correlation to perceptual scores, namely: Pearson's correlation coefficient (PCC), Spearman's rank-ordered correlation coefficient (SROCC), Kendall's rank-order correlation coefficient (KROCC), the root-mean-squared error (RMSE), and the mean absolute error (MAE) [26].

Fig. 5 Objective VQA rate-distortion curves for (a) $PSNR_{611}$ vs log (bitrate), (b) SSIM vs log (bitrate), (c) VMAF-4K vs log (bitrate), (d) VIF vs log(bitrate), (e) MS-SSIM of vs log (bitrate), (f) PSNR-HVS vs log (bitrate) and (g) PSNR-HVS-M vs log (bitrate) of mean dataset values.

TABLE III.A CORRELATION PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF OBJECTIVE AND SUBJECTIVE VQA RATINGS

Objective VQA Metric	PSNR				SSIM				VMAF-4K				VIF			
	X264	X265	VVC	SVT-AV1	X264	X265	VVC	SVT-AV1	X264	X265	VVC	SVT-AV1	X264	X265	VVC	SVT-AV1
PCC	0.795	0.799	0.756	0.892	0.652	0.646	0.649	0.616	0.914	0.911	0.846	0.853	0.892	0.896	0.845	0.829
SROCC	0.796	0.769	0.756	0.906	0.705	0.667	0.668	0.592	0.901	0.85	0.821	0.804	0.906	0.889	0.841	0.793
KROCC	0.615	0.564	0.573	0.769	0.534	0.497	0.466	0.43	0.756	0.731	0.639	0.624	0.769	0.725	0.639	0.611
RMSE	0.633	0.503	0.706	0.472	0.792	0.638	0.819	0.891	0.423	0.345	0.645	0.668	0.472	0.372	0.645	0.697
MAE	0.503	0.391	0.485	0.364	0.628	0.486	0.569	0.767	0.308	0.236	0.511	0.598	0.364	0.252	0.469	0.637

TABLE III.B CORRELATION PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF OBJECTIVE AND SUBJECTIVE VQA RATINGS

Objective VQA Metric	MS_SSIM				PSNR_HVS				PSNR_HVSM				
	CODEC	X264	X265	VVC	SVT-AV1	X264	X265	VVC	SVT-AV1	X264	X265	VVC	SVT-AV1
PCC		0.867	0.842	0.787	0.8	0.829	0.822	0.784	0.783	0.875	0.875	0.837	0.849
SROCC		0.905	0.844	0.816	0.819	0.820	0.782	0.767	0.708	0.902	0.866	0.838	0.797
KROCC		0.763	0.658	0.593	0.631	0.669	0.598	0.579	0.553	0.769	0.684	0.633	0.591
RMSE		0.521	0.451	0.707	0.733	0.585	0.476	0.709	0.747	0.505	0.405	0.654	0.669
MAE		0.383	0.335	0.473	0.663	0.426	0.358	0.507	0.647	0.358	0.300	0.497	0.579

* The correlation fidelity of the objective VQA metrics compared to the subjective MOS increases with values closer to 1 for PCC, SROCC and KROCC correlation indices (conversely, for RMSE and MAE, lower values correspond to higher correlation). The highest correlation score attained by each codec for each of the five correlation metrics used in this study, across all objective VQA methods, is highlighted in bold fonts.

Fig. 6 Relationship between objective VQA metrics' scores and subjective VQA ratings (MOS)

Fig. 6 illustrates the relationship between objective video quality assessment metrics and subjective quality evaluation measurements (in MOS). The scattered dots represent the subjective scores, whereas the dashed line is obtained by fitting the subjective scores using the derived objective metrics. Since logistic functions are capable of capturing this relationship, we utilize the measurements to fit a logistic function of the following form:

$$f(X) = \frac{l}{1+e^{(-k(X-X_0))}} \quad (1)$$

Where $f(X)$ is the predicted MOS value based on the objective score X . l , k , and X_0 are the fitting parameters.

Table III shows the evaluation results for PSNR, SSIM, VIF, VMAF-4K, MS-SSIM, PSNR-HVSA, and PSNR-HVS-M according to the aforementioned methods. Based on the obtained results, VMAF-4K exhibits the highest correlation to the subjective scores across most codecs and all evaluation criteria. It achieved the highest correlation with the subjective MOS values (PCC: 0.853-0.914, SROCC: 0.804-0.901, KROCC: 0.624-0.756) and the lowest error metrics (RMSE: 0.345-0.668, MAE: 0.236-0.598). VIF had the second-best performance, followed by the MS-SSIM, PSNR-HVS-M, PSNR-HVS, PSNR and SSIM.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we performed a subjective assessment of video quality, specifically focusing on individual codec's compression efficiency. Using video sequences of various content and bitrates levels, we compared the most widely used (x264, x265) and emerging (VVC, SVT-AV1) video codecs. The findings demonstrated that the VVC surpasses all other investigated compression standards in terms of BD-rate, using both mean opinion scores and objective VQA metrics outcomes. Moreover, we conducted a correlation analysis, comparing the MOS values with different objective VQA algorithms, namely PSNR, PSNR-HVS, PSNR-HVS-M, SSIM, MS-SSIM, VMAF-4K, and VIF. Our findings indicate that the VMAF-4K and VIF measures offer the strongest correlation between the objective and the subjective assessments.

For future work, we intend to extend our experiments to include different viewing scenarios with larger numbers of participants. We also plan to conduct a subjective VQA study for 360° videos and construct a 360° video viewing dataset to assist in 360° video streaming research [27][28].

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